

Photolysis of Substituted Benzylideneacenaphthenones

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Substituted benzylideneacenaphthenones were photolysed in benzene in presence of air. Cyclodehydrogenation led to substituted-benzochrysenes as well as photo-oxidative cleavage of benzylidene double bond leading to naphthalene-1,8-dicarboxylic acid anhydride as the major product. Photolysis of acenaphthenone also gave naphthalene-1,8-dicarboxylic acid anhydride under the same condition in which the benzylidene analogues were irradiated.

STOBBE¹ observed that dibenzalsuccinic acid anhydride on irradiation by uv light underwent smooth cyclodehydrogenation. Mallory *et al.*² reported that the yields were better in the presence of oxygen, poor in the atmosphere of air whereas it did not go in nitrogen atmosphere. A number of examples of the photo-oxidative cleavage of the double bonds through dioxetene intermediates³⁻⁷ have been reported. The present investigations were undertaken with a view to study the behaviour of substituted-benzylideneacenaphthenones (2a-c) which were irradiated in benzene solutions using pyrex reactors in the atmosphere of oxygen.

Thus, benzylideneacenaphthenone (2a) on photolysis and subsequent column chromatography gave an unidentified liquid, unreacted material (2a), 10(*H*)oxo-10,11-methanochrysenes (4a)⁸ and a geometrical isomer of 2a, naphthalene-1,8-dicarboxylic acid anhydride (11) besides unidentified polymer (Table 1).

In a similar fashion *o*-chlorobenzylideneacenaphthenone (2b) on photolysis and column chromatography afforded an unidentified liquid, starting material (2b), another unidentified product, 1-chloro-10(*H*)oxo-10,11-methanochrysenes (4b)⁸ and naphthalene-1,8-dicarboxylic acid anhydride (11) (Table 1). However, 2-chloro-5-nitrobenzylidene

acenaphthenone (2c) in benzene provided an unidentified liquid product, starting material (2c), 2-nitro-10(*H*)oxo-10,11-methanochrysenes (5) and naphthalene-1,8-dicarboxylic acid anhydride (11) (Table 1).

In order to confirm the proposed mechanism (Chart 1) acenaphthenone (1) was also subjected to photolysis in benzene and subsequent column chromatography provided naphthalene-1,8-dicarboxylic acid anhydride (11) alongwith 8-formyl-1-naphthoic acid lactone (14) (Table 1).

Experimental

M.ps. and b ps. are uncorrected. Nmr spectra were run on Perkin-Elmer (90 MHz) and Varian T-60 spectrometers and ir spectra run on a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer. Silica gel and petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) (B.D.H.) were used throughout the investigation.

Benzylidene acenaphthenone (2a): A mixture of acenaphthenone (3.44 g, 0.02 mol; prepared in 55.30% yield according to Fieser's method¹⁷) and benzaldehyde (2.12 g, 0.2 mol) in ethanol (25 ml) was cooled to 0° in an ice-salt bath. Sodium hydroxide (2.0 g) in ethanol (18.0 ml) was then added dropwise

TABLE 1—DETAILS OF PHOTOLYSIS PROCEDURE WITH PRODUCTS ISOLATED AFTER COLUMN CHROMATOGRAPHY AND YIELD

Compd. no.	Wt. of compd (mg) (Vol. of solvent, ml)	Time h	Unidentified product	Unreacted product (Yield)	Cyclised product (Yield)	Isomer of starting material mg/(%)	11 mg/(%)	14 mg/(%)	Polymer mg
2a	300 (300)	50	Traces	2a (10 mg, 3.3%)	4a (50 mg, 16.8%)	80 (26.7)	70 (30.7)	—	—
2b	500 (500)	9	Traces of 1st., 2nd. fractions	2b (100 mg, 20%)	4b (70 mg, 14.1%)	5 (1)	70 (20.6)	—	15
2c	450 (450)	5	Trace	2c (200 mg, 44.4%)	5 (200 mg, 44.4%)	—	5 (2.0)	—	12
1	1.0 g (500)	40	—	1 (600 mg, 60%)	—	—	100 (8.48)	70 (6.0)	—

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Chart 1

to the reaction mixture whose colour successively changed to red, light green and yellow. Stirring was continued for further 1 h at room temperature and the content poured into cold water. The resulting solid was filtered under suction, washed with water until free from base and crystallised in ethanol/petroleum ether to light yellow crystals (4.5 g, 87%), m.p. 122–23° (Found: C, 88.7; H, 4.5. $C_{19}H_{13}O$ requires: C, 89.0; H, 4.7%); R_f 0.4 (silica gel/benzene–petroleum ether, 1:1); ν_{max} (nujol) 1700 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ ($CDCl_3$ +TFA) 7.86 (1H, s, benzal proton) and 7.53–8.23 (11H, m, rest of ArH).

***o*-Chlorobenzylidene acenaphthenone (2b):** It was prepared from acenaphthenone (3.44 g, 0.02 mol), *o*-chlorobenzaldehyde (2.59 g, 0.02 mol) in ethanol (25 ml) and sodium hydroxide (2.0 g) in ethanol (18 ml), following the procedure described for 2a. The product was recrystallised from petroleum ether–benzene (70:30), (5.3 g, 91%), m.p. 179.8° (Found: C, 78.3; H, 3.7; Cl, 11.9. $C_{19}H_{11}OCl$ requires: C, 78.5; H, 3.8, Cl, 12.1%); R_f 0.3 (silica gel/benzene–petroleum ether, 1:1); ν_{max} (KBr) 1690 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ ($CDCl_3$ +TFA) 7.96 (1H, s, benzal proton) and 7.20–8.20 (10H, m, rest of ArH).

2-Chloro-5-nitrobenzylidene acenaphthenone (2c): To a mixture of acenaphthenone (0.84 g, 0.005 mol) and 2-chloro-5-nitrobenzaldehyde¹⁸ (0.93 g, 0.005 mol; prepared by the nitration of *o*-chlorobenzaldehyde in 80% yield, m.p. 78–9°) was added acetic anhydride (20 ml) and refluxed for 4 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and poured into crushed ice. On usual workup the solid product revealed two spots on tlc which were separated by crystallisation in petroleum ether. One of the products was acetyl acenaphthenol, m.p. 114–19°;

ν_{max} (KBr) 1750 (C=O), 1350 and 1230 cm^{-1} (CH). The other product was purified by passing through a column of silica gel to obtain a yellow coloured compound (2c; 0.2 g, 9.2%), m.p. 218°d (Found: C, 67.5; H, 2.9; N, 4.1; Cl, 10.6. $C_{19}H_{10}NO_2Cl$ requires: C, 67.9; H, 3.0; N, 4.2; Cl, 10.6%); R_f 0.5 (silica gel/benzene); ν_{max} (KBr) 1710 (C=O), 1560, 1340, (NO₂); δ ($CDCl_3$ +TFA) 8.60 (1H, d, H₈), 8.23 (1H, d, H₄), 8.12 (1H, dd, H₆), 7.87 (1H, s, benzal proton) and 7.40–8.30 (m, rest of ArH).

General method of photolysis: A pyrex photo-reactor equipped with a gas budding leak, a condenser with a guard tube and 125 KW high pressure mercury vapour lamp (Philips) in the inner prove was placed in a water-bath in which flow of water was regulated to effect the external cooling. The reactor was charged for every reaction with a solution of known concentration of compound to be photolysed (2a–c, Table 1) and the lamp was switched on. The progress of the reaction was monitored by taking out aliquot of the reaction mixture at regular intervals. After completion of the reaction, the reaction mixture was taken out and solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure. The resulting residue was fed onto the column of silica gel and eluted with solvents of increasing polarity. Small fractions (20 ml) of solvent were collected from the column and those having single spots were crystallised again.

The physical data of all the photo products isolated are discussed below.

10(H)-Oxo-10,11-methanochrysenes (4a): Mass spectrum exhibited molecular ion peak at m/e 254 which was followed by m/e 226 ($M-CO$). However, due to its poor solubility nmr spectrum could not be recorded. Its ir spectrum contained bands at 3020 (Ar), 1700 (C=O) and 1600 cm^{-1} . The compound melted at 284–85°.

Stereoisomer of 2a: Its structure was established by the presence of bands at 3020 (CH), 1710 (C=O), 1600 cm^{-1} ; it appeared to be the geometrical isomer of 2a. It was further confirmed by its 60 MHz nmr spectrum indicating signals at δ 8.15–7.15 and obviously it could not be chrysenes system in which one could expect the bay protons to resonate downfield than δ 8.15 around δ 8.70^{9,10}; the compound melted at 215–16°.

Naphthalene-1,8-dicarboxylic acid anhydride (11): Its ir spectrum was comparable to that reported in the literature¹⁰ suggesting its structure to be 11 which was further corroborated by its 60 MHz nmr spectrum consisting of a 2H doublet of doublet at δ 8.0 which was assigned to the proton H-3 and H-6. The 4H doublet of doublet at δ 8.8 was assigned to the protons H-2, H-4, H-5 and H-7 exhibiting *ortho* and *meta* coupling of appropriate values¹¹. The mass spectrum showed fragments at m/e 198, 154 ($M-CO_2$) and 126 (154–CO) which finally established the structure of the compound unequivocally, m.p. 270–71¹².

1-Chloro-10(H)-oxo-10,11-methanochrysene (4b): The appearance of an ir absorption band at 1730 cm^{-1} (C=O in five-membered ring) suggested its structure as **4b** which was further corroborated by its nmr spectrum, consisting of a 1H doublet at δ 8.67 which has been assigned to H-4 proton. The downfield shift of H-4 may be ascribed to 'Bay effect'¹⁸. It was followed by another doublet of doublet at δ 8.37 which was assigned to the proton H-9. The 1H singlet at δ 8.33 was ascribed to H-11 proton. The 6H multiplet at δ 8.20–7.05 could be traced to the protons H-2, H-3, H-5, H-6, H-7 and H-8, thus confirming the structure as **4b**. Its mass spectrum contained molecular ion peaks at m/e 290 and 288 in the ratio of 1 : 3 and this isotopic cluster a characteristic for one chlorine atom in the molecule. The molecular ion peaks at m/e 262 and 260 (M-CO) again showed that the chlorine atom was intact. The compound with shining crystals melted at $212-13^\circ$.

Geometrical isomer of 2b: Its ir bands at 1720 (CO), 1640 , 1620 and 1600 cm^{-1} suggested the structure; moreover analogy with the product from **2a** also approved of this idea. It melted at $206-07^\circ$.

2-Nitro-10(H)-oxo-10,11-methanochrysene (5): Its ir spectrum contained bands at 1760 and 1730 cm^{-1} C=O doublet (Fermi resonance due to 850 cm^{-1} band) suggested 5-membered cyclic carboxyl in its molecules. Its nmr spectrum (TFA) consisted of a signals at δ 8.90 as a 1H doublet ascribed to the proton H-4. The next 1H doublet of doublet at δ 8.60 was assigned to the proton H-9 whereas doublet at δ 8.30 may be assigned to the proton H-1. The proton H-11 resonated as a 1H singlet at δ 8.35. The protons H-5 and H-6 were located as a 2H AB quartet centred at δ 7.95. The protons H-3, H-7 and H-8 resonated as a 3H multiplet at δ 7.70–7.30 thereby confirming the structure as **5**, m.p. $245-46^\circ$.

8-Formylnaphth-1-oic acid (14): Its ir spectrum consisted of bands at 3275 (CH) and 1675 cm^{-1} (C=O) suggesting the proposed structure. Its nmr spectrum in DMSO- d_6 consisted of two 1H doublets of doublet each at δ 8.50 and 8.30 which have been assigned to the protons H-2 and H-4 respectively. The 4H multiplet at δ 8.30–7.50 was tagged to the protons H-5, H-3 and H-7, H-3 and H-6. The 2H broad singlet at δ 7.0 was assigned to the benzylic and OH protons. Appearance of ion peaks at m/e 200(57), 199(56), 172(100), 156(36), 155(87) and 127(99) in its mass spectrum finally confirmed the assigned structure. The ir data tally well with the values reported in the literature¹⁴ for this compound. It melted at $168-69^\circ$.

Results and Discussion

Absence of reductive dimerisation products suggested that transitions are lower in energy than the $n-\pi^*$ transitions. Since photocyclisation was affected in an atmosphere of oxygen, two reaction pathways can be visualised: (i) photocyclodehy-

dration and (ii) photo-oxidative degradation. In the case of pathway (i), the halogen was intact in the cyclised product from **2b**. It is logical to consider partial double bond character of Ar-Cl. However, in the case of **2c** halogen becomes liable due to the presence of a nitro group in its *para*-position and thus it can be inferred that cyclisation has taken place by the loss of halogen.

The oxidative degradation occurs through the attack of singlet oxygen on the C=C bond followed by the fission of the resulting dioxetane (Chart 2). The initially formed acenaphthenedione^{15,16} then undergoes Norrish type-I fission followed by

Chart 2

hydrogen abstraction from the solvent (C_6H_6) although difficult but not unusual, providing naphthalene-1,8-dicarboxyaldehyde and the latter gets oxidised to subsequent products in an atmosphere of oxygen.

TABLE 2—ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS OF PHOTOPRODUCTS

Compd. no.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				Mol. formula
	C	H	N	OI	
4a	89.7 (89.8)	8.9 (8.9)	—	—	$C_{11}H_{10}O$
4b	78.8 (79.0)	8.0 (8.1)	—	12.5 (12.9)	$C_{11}H_9OCl$
5	76.2 (76.25)	8.0 (8.01)	4.6 (4.68)	—	$C_{11}H_9Mo_2$
2a	88.7 (89.1)	4.5 (4.7)	—	—	$C_{11}H_{12}O$
2b (isomer)	78.8 (78.5)	8.7 (8.8)	—	11.9 (12.2)	$C_{11}H_{11}OCl$

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